

EXPERIMENTAL-THEORETICAL ANALYSIS OF MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF PERFORATED COMPOSITE SANDWICH PANELS FOR AIRCRAFT ENGINE NACELLE

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ABSTRACT

This work is dedicated to experimental-theoretical analysis of mechanical properties of sandwich panels made of fibrous polymer composite materials. The analysis of influence of perforation on mechanical properties of fiberglass sandwich panels with tubular core was performed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Today sandwich panels made of fibrous polymer composite materials are widely used in aviation industry for load bearing elements. Also they perform special functions such as sound and thermal insulation, damping, radioparent and aerodynamic. A promising area of the use of composite sandwich panels in manufacture of aircraft turbojet engines is acoustic liners in the nacelle. For fulfilling the noise reduction function, there are different types of core inside sandwich panels – tubular, honeycomb or cellular structure (Fig.1).

The behavior of honeycomb structures was investigated, for example, in [1-3] using the finite element method (FEM). Today the most researches are devoted to mechanical behavior of hexagonal cell filler (honeycomb-core) made of metallic materials and based on the theory of strength of materials with some assumptions [4-6].

The present work is dedicated to analysis of influence of perforation (which occupies up to 10% of the total area) on mechanical properties of fiberglass sandwich panels with tubular core.

2 STRUCTURE AND MODEL OF SANDWICH PANELS

The numerical analysis of stress-strain state of sandwich panel under various conditions of loading was obtained with ANSYS Workbench software. For this simulation the 3D parametric models of sandwich panels corresponding to full-scale samples used for mechanical tests were created [7].

Figure 1: Types of core: tubular (a), honeycomb (b), cellular (c).

Dimensions of the modelled samples were 150 mm × 350 mm. Thanks to symmetry of the modelled specimens, simulations can be reduced by investigation of their halves only. Gripping fixtures, used for installing a sample in a testing machine, were also modelled in order to reproduce a character of load application in real experiments. These fixtures consisted of steel pads, a gasket, a seal and bolts, as illustrated in Fig. 2. The fixture system with 10 bolts as well as a straight shape of the specimen (without fillets) provided a uniform stress field and non-critical stress levels in the damaged region.

Figure 2: 3D FE model of sandwich panel with fixture for experimental testing.

The studied sandwich panel consists of three-ply 90/0/90 and two-ply 90/0 laminate skins and tubes with 20/-20 laminate faces (Fig. 3). Initial mechanical properties and strength characteristics of the materials used in numerical studies were obtained in in-house tests and are shown in Tables 1 and 2.

As sandwich panel with tubular fibreglass core were composed of laminates with different types of perforation, thickness and orientation of plies, for numerical studies of their mechanical properties and performance under specified loading it was necessary to obtain effective properties of each laminate.

The calculations of effective elastic and strength characteristics of fibreglass perforated layered shells were obtained with ANSYS Mechanical software. Different reinforcement schemes (70/-70, 90/0, 90/0/90) and two types of perforation were considered.

The first type of perforation is dense perforation with a distance between holes is about 9 mm, diameter of holes is 2.0 mm. Perforation of the second type is sparse, with the same diameter of holes and distance of about 18 mm between them. A three-ply skin and adjacent tube faces have the former type of perforation, while inner faces of the tubes are perforated with the latter one.

Figure 3: Layout of internal structure of sandwich panel

Material	E_X , GPa	E_Y , GPa	E_Z , GPa	ν_{XY}	ν_{YZ}	ν_{XZ}	G_{XY} , GPa	G_{YZ} , GPa	G_{XZ} , GPa
Fibre-glass prepreg	24.6	18.6	6.0	0.15	0.18	0.42	4.0	3.0	3.0
Resin	2.9	-	-	0.36	-	-	-	-	-

Table 1: Properties of materials used in numerical studies

Material	σ_X , MPa		σ_Y , MPa	
	tension	compression	tension	compression
Fibre-glass prepreg	600	450	300	295
Resin	30-45		30-45	

Table 2: Strength characteristics of materials

3 EFFECTIVE PROPERTIES OF PERFORATED AND NON-PERFORATED LAMINATES

For non-perforated laminates effective properties were calculated with the help of MathCAD software using the theory of anisotropic plates, based on initial properties of materials (Table 1) [8, 9].

Obtaining effective properties of the perforated laminates can be singled out as a separate task since direct modelling of such structural elements is connected with computational difficulties due to a large number of small-sized curved areas (holes) that require a fine FE mesh.

As perforation was periodic, representative volume elements (RVE) of the laminates could be considered for assessment of their effective properties. Their dimensions were chosen as 60 mm × 60 mm to include a significant number of perforation holes (Fig.4). The latter were calculated using numerical studies with different type of load applied to RVE.

Figure 3: FE mesh of representative volume elements (RVE) of the laminates

The considered laminates were orthotropic, characterized by nine independent elastic constants: the Young's moduli E_X , E_Y , E_Z , Poisson's ratios ν_{XY} , ν_{YZ} , ν_{XZ} , and shear moduli G_{XY} , G_{YZ} , G_{XZ} . Three types of numerical experiments were implemented for each RVE of the perforated laminates: tension along axes X and Y to determine the effective Young's moduli and Poisson's ratios, and pure shear in the XY plane to calculate the shear moduli. In each case the laminate RVE model was subjected to a kinematic loading condition of 1 mm displacement on the corresponding border. The problem was solved with ANSYS Mechanical software employing Shell281 finite elements. This element has 8 nodes with 6 degrees of freedom in each node.

The homogenized constants of the perforated laminates – the elastic moduli and Poisson's coefficient – were obtained with the following formulas:

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_x^* &= \frac{\langle \sigma_X \rangle}{\varepsilon_X}, \quad E_y^* = \frac{\langle \sigma_Y \rangle}{\varepsilon_Y}, \quad E_z^* = \frac{\langle \sigma_Z \rangle}{\varepsilon_Z}, \\
 G_{XY}^* &= \frac{\langle \tau_{XY} \rangle}{\gamma_{XY}}, \quad G_{YZ}^* = \frac{\langle \tau_{YZ} \rangle}{\gamma_{YZ}}, \quad G_{XZ}^* = \frac{\langle \tau_{XZ} \rangle}{\gamma_{XZ}}, \\
 \nu_{XY} &= \left| \frac{\varepsilon_Y}{\varepsilon_X} \right|, \quad \nu_{YZ} = \left| \frac{\varepsilon_Z}{\varepsilon_Y} \right|, \quad \nu_{XZ} = \left| \frac{\varepsilon_Z}{\varepsilon_X} \right|,
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where strains ε_X , ε_Y , ε_Z and γ_{ij} were predetermined in the numerical experiments.

The mean stress values were calculated using the following relation:

$$\langle \sigma \rangle = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_i V_i}{V_M}, \tag{2}$$

where n is number of finite elements in the RVE, σ_i is stress in the i^{th} finite element, V_i is its volume, V_M is the representative volume.

The effective mechanical characteristics of the perforated laminates obtained with the discussed numerical homogenisation are summarized in Table 3 and Table 4.

Laminate	Perforation	E_x , GPa	E_y , GPa	E_z , GPa	ν_{xy}	ν_{yz}	ν_{xz}	G_{xy} , GPa	G_{yz} , GPa	G_{xz} , GPa
2 plies 70/-70	No	20.5	16.1	6.0	0.23	0.18	0.42	6.3	3.0	3.0
2 plies 90/0	No	21.6	21.6	6.0	0.13	0.18	0.42	4.0	3.0	3.0
3 plies 90/0/90	No	20.6	22.6	6.0	0.12	0.18	0.42	4.0	3.0	3.0
3 plies 90/0/90	Type 1 (dense)	14.3	18.4	6.0	0.2	0.18	0.42	1.3	3.0	3.0
2 plies 70/-70	Type 1 (dense)	15.9	12.5	6.0	0.2	0.18	0.42	1.5	3.0	3.0
2 plies 70/-70	Type 2 (sparse)	19.5	15.2	6.0	0.3	0.18	0.42	1.7	3.0	3.0

Table 3: Effective elastic properties of laminates (x – weft direction, y – warp direction).

Laminate	Perforation	$[\sigma]_x^+$, MPa	$[\sigma]_y^+$, MPa
2 plies 70/-70	No	588.9	303.0
2 plies 90/0	No	345.5	259.2
3 plies 90/0/90	No	299.7	398.7
3 plies 90/0/90	Type 1 (dense)	136.0	327.5
2 plies 70/-70	Type 1 (dense)	100.0	204.0
2 plies 70/-70	Type 2 (sparse)	70.0	207.0

Table 4: Effective strength of laminates (x – weft direction, y – warp direction).

4 EXPERIMENTAL RESEARCH OF EFFECTIVE PROPERTIES OF PERFORATED LAMINATES

Verification of the proposed numerical algorithm and obtained results was carried out with the help of tensile tests of special specimens of 2-ply laminates according to ASTM D 882 (Standard Test Method for Tensile Properties of Thin Plastic Sheeting). Static tests were conducted on Zwick / Roell ProLine Z100 testing machine (Fig. 4). Tensile stress-strain curves for tested specimens are given in Figures 5-7. Table 5 shows the values of calculated and experimental effective elastic modulus of perforated laminates.

Figure 4 - Tensile testing of perforated laminate

Figure 5: Tensile stress-strain curves for perforated laminate in warp direction (2 plies 90/90)

Figure 6: Tensile stress-strain curves for perforated laminate in weft direction (2 plies 0/0)

Figure 7: Tensile stress-strain curves for perforated laminate with 2 plies 70/-70.

Laminate	E_y , GPa	
	Experimental data	Numerical simulation
2 plies 0/0	17,3	18,7
2 plies 90/90	12,3	12,9
2 plies 70/-70	10,8	11,6

Table 5: Effective elastic modulus of perforated laminates

5 NUMERICAL MODELLING OF MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF SANDWICH PANELS

The main numerical studies included development of finite-elements models of the considered sandwich panel specimens under tensile loading. FE analysis was implemented employing the obtained effective properties of laminates for each structural component of the panels. Meshing was automatically implemented in ANSYS Workbench using tetrahedral elements. The mesh density was considered optimal when the difference between the results of successive calculations with a refined mesh did not exceed 5 - 10%.

A mathematical formulation corresponded to the elasticity theory of anisotropic solids:

$$\sigma_{ij,j} = 0, \quad \varepsilon_{ij} = \frac{1}{2}(u_{i,j} + u_{j,i}), \quad \sigma_{ij} = C_{ijkl}\varepsilon_{kl} . \quad (3)$$

The boundary conditions used for tension loading were symmetric on a border Γ_1 (see Fig. 8):

$$\begin{cases} U_Y|_{\Gamma_1} = 0 \\ \tau_{XY}|_{\Gamma_1} = \tau_{YZ}|_{\Gamma_1} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Displacements along axes X and Y on a border Γ_2 were constrained:

$$\begin{cases} U_Y|_{\Gamma_2} = 0 \\ U_X|_{\Gamma_2} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Thereby gripping of the test equipment as well as presence of a polymeric filler inside were taken into account. Loads were applied along the tension axis to each of the metallic bolts (boundary Γ_2):

$$P_Y|_{\Gamma_2} = 100 \text{ kN}$$

Figure 8: Boundary conditions (a) and calculated total displacements in mm (b)

As a result of the numerical simulation, stress and strain fields were obtained. Figure 8,b shows the calculated total displacements in the samples of panel under load of 100 kN. The stress-strain analysis allows us to determine the averaged stresses in the samples and effective elastic modulus of panels. The magnitudes of breaking loads for each specimen were obtained by comparison the maximal stress values and strength characteristics from Table 2.

6 EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS OF SANDWICH PANEL SAMPLES

The results of simulation were compared to results of samples tension tests described in [10, 11]. The tests were performed on a universal electromechanical testing system Instron 5882. The applied displacement speed was 5 mm/min for tension tests and 2 mm/min for compression tests. The results of the experiments are summarized in Table 6.

Specimen	Breaking load P_{\max} , kN	Elongation at rupture, mm
1	100.7	9.4
2	100.7	10.1
3	96.5	9.2

Table 6: Results of tension tests of sandwich panel samples

As dimensions of the produced specimens may differ due to their manufacture, the values of breaking load cannot be used directly for comparison of their strength. Thus, it is essential to introduce new normalized value that will take into account the dimensional variability and its association with the breaking-load magnitudes. The effective tensile strength value can be employed as such normalized strength parameter; it can be calculated based on the breaking load P_{\max} (in kN) and mean geometrical parameters of the samples:

$$\sigma_b = \frac{P_{\max}}{bh} \cdot 10^3 \text{ (in MPa)}, \quad (6)$$

where \bar{b} is mean width of the specimen's working zone, \bar{h} is mean thickness of the specimen (both – in mm).

These parameters were measured for each manufactured sample. In our FE studies they were defined by geometry of the developed 3D models. Table 7 provide a comparison between the values of effective strength measured in tests and calculated numerically with the FE model. The numerically calculated breaking loads were defined by the weakest structural elements.

	Specimen	Working zone width, mm	Thickness, mm	Breaking load, kN	Effective tensile strength, MPa	Mean effective strength, MPa
		\bar{b}	\bar{h}	P_{\max}	σ_b	$\bar{\sigma}_b$
Experimental data	1	101.21	25.4	74.4	28.9	29.9
	2	100.23	25.3	77.2	30.3	
	3	100.15	25.1	76.8	30.5	
Numerical simulations		150	23.99	98	27.2	27.2

Table 7: Parameters and effective strength values for sandwich panels

7 CONCLUSION

This work is dedicated to experimental-theoretical analysis of mechanical properties of sandwich panels made of fibrous polymer composite materials. The analysis of influence of perforation on mechanical properties of fiberglass sandwich panels with tubular core was performed.

The calculations of effective elastic and strength characteristics of fiberglass perforated laminates were obtained with ANSYS Mechanical software. Different reinforcement schemes (70/-70, 90/0, 90/0/90) and two types of perforation were considered. It was shown that the perforation leads to decrease of material stiffness up to 30%, and strength – up to 40-60%.

Verification of the proposed numerical algorithm and obtained results was carried out with the help of tensile tests of special specimens according to ASTM D 882.

The calculated effective properties of laminates were used for the numerical analysis of the stress-strain state of the entire sandwich panel under various conditions of loading in ANSYS Workbench. For this simulation the 3D parametric models of sandwich panels corresponding to full-scale samples used for mechanical tests were created. The effective tensile ultimate strength and elastic modulus of panels were determined. The influence of perforation on their mechanical properties was evaluated

The results of numerical simulations of mechanical behaviour of sandwich panels were compared with the test data. Good correlation was found.

The created numerical models and the results of this work will be used for new fundamental investigation dedicated to the development of experimental and theoretical principles of the mechanical analysis of self-diagnosable (smart-) materials based on optical fibers. These elements embedded in sandwich panels will allow controlling the mechanical behavior of constructions in real-time mode.

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